

Medication adherence and disease activity in patients with ankylosing spondylitis: A pilot study

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Abstract

Ankylosing spondylitis (AS) is a chronic inflammatory rheumatic disease requiring long-term pharmacological treatment and active patient engagement.

Low to moderate levels of treatment adherence were observed in most participants, while disease activity was predominantly moderate to high. A statistically significant moderate positive association was identified between reported adherence and symptom burden, indicating higher adherence among patients with more active disease. Educational level emerged as a key determinant of adherence, with lower adherence observed in patients with higher education. Disease activity was significantly influenced by sex, comorbidities, smoking status, physical inactivity, and the use of biological therapy. These findings suggest that adherence behavior is dynamic and strongly driven by symptom severity rather than functioning as an independent predictor of disease control.

The results highlight the importance of continuous monitoring of medication-taking behavior and the need for targeted pharmaceutical care interventions, particularly during periods of lower symptom intensity. Larger longitudinal studies are warranted to further clarify adherence patterns and their impact on long-term outcomes.

Keywords

adherence behavior, ankylosing spondylitis, influencing factors, pharmacological treatment, symptom severity

Introduction

Ankylosing spondylitis (AS) is a chronic, immune-mediated inflammatory rheumatic disease that primarily affects the axial skeleton and leads to progressive pain in the lower back, stiffness, and functional limitations. The disease usually affects young people, most often between the ages of 20 and 30 years (Zimba et al. 2024). The global prevalence of AS varies between 0.3% and 1.4%. A trend of increasing numbers of affected individuals with

increasing distance from the Equator is observed: from 0.20% in Southeast Asia to 1.61% in northern Arctic communities (Bakland et al. 2013). For Bulgaria, there are no accurate statistics, but based on data from international studies, it is assumed that the number of people with AS is between 20,000 and 30,000, which corresponds to 0.3% to 0.4% of the country's population (Andreev et al. 2018). The insufficient reliable information is probably due to a substantial proportion of undiagnosed patients and delays in establishing the correct diagnosis.

Untreated AS can progress to serious structural damage, deformities, and permanent disability, which has a significant impact on the quality of life, work capacity, and social development of patients with AS (National Council on Prices and Reimbursement of Medicinal Products 2019). The disease represents a serious long-term burden both for affected individuals and as a socioeconomic burden for health systems (Zhang et al. 2024).

Current therapeutic strategies in AS aim to achieve control of inflammation, alleviate symptoms, prevent structural damage, and preserve physical function, as well as the patient's social and professional integration, taking into account the young age of those affected (van der Heijde et al. 2017; Ward et al. 2019). Treatment should be strictly guided in accordance with the defined target, usually aimed at achieving sustained remission and low disease activity, applying the current recommendations of ASAS (Assessment of SpondyloArthritis international Society) and EULAR (European Alliance of Associations for Rheumatology) for the treatment and control of AS (Ramiro et al. 2023). International recommendations emphasize the need for long-term pharmacological therapy, including non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medicinal products and biological and targeted synthetic disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (Sepriano et al. 2017). Non-pharmacological approaches are based on regular physical activity and control of health-behavioral factors such as smoking, diet, weight control, and sleep hygiene (Andreev 2025).

The effectiveness of the applied therapy in real clinical practice, particularly in chronic rheumatologic diseases, depends to a significant extent on the patient's adherence to the prescribed treatment (Vrijens et al. 2012). Medication adherence represents the extent to which the patient's behavior corresponds to the therapeutic recommendations agreed upon with the healthcare professional (World Health Organization 2003). Conceptually, it includes initiation, implementation, and persistence of medication therapy – i.e., starting therapy with the intake of the first dose, the extent to which dosing corresponds to the regimen prescribed by the physician, and continuing therapy over time (Vrijens et al. 2012). In chronic inflammatory diseases, non-adherence to therapy is a common problem and is associated with poorer disease control, higher disease activity, more frequent flares, and increased use of health resources (Chaudri 2004). Patients with AS face specific challenges, such as the long-term nature of treatment, polypharmacy, adverse drug reactions, and subjective perception of symptoms, which can negatively affect therapeutic engagement.

The assessment of disease activity in ankylosing spondylitis in clinical practice is most often performed using validated composite indices. One of the most widely used is the Bath Ankylosing Spondylitis Disease Activity Index (BASDAI), which reflects the patient's subjective perception of symptoms (Garrett et al. 1994). Available data from prospective observations in patients on biological therapy show a significant inverse relationship between self-reported adherence and BASDAI (Youssef and El Rafey 2021).

Despite established strategies for treatment and monitoring, adherence to therapy in chronic rheumatologic diseases remains unsatisfactory, and the available data specifically for AS are limited and methodologically heterogeneous, which determines the need to expand research in this field. Systematic assessment of adherence and the factors that determine it is essential for optimizing long-term therapeutic outcomes in patients with ankylosing spondylitis.

Clarifying the relationship between medication adherence and disease activity in real-world settings is important for identifying modifiable factors and early recognition of patients at risk of treatment failure, as well as for developing evidence-based interventions, including structured education and a multidisciplinary approach in which the pharmacist may have a role in monitoring and supporting therapy.

Aim

This pilot study aims to assess the level of medication adherence in patients with ankylosing spondylitis and its relationship with disease activity, measured by BASDAI, as well as the factors influencing them.

Materials and methods

Study design

An observational, cross-sectional survey study was conducted to assess the level of medication adherence and disease activity in patients with AS. The study was carried out in community pharmacies in the Ruse region, Bulgaria, during the period from November 2024–September 2025.

Study population

The study included 66 patients with a confirmed diagnosis of ankylosing spondylitis. The inclusion criteria were:

- age ≥ 18 years;
 - residing in the Ruse region;
 - confirmed diagnosis of ankylosing spondylitis (M45);
 - prescribed and ongoing pharmacological therapy;
 - signed informed consent to participate in the study.
- The exclusion criteria were:
- presence of severe cognitive impairment;
 - individuals with hearing or visual impairment.
 - inability to complete the survey instruments independently;
 - refusal to participate in the study.

All patients receiving active pharmacological treatment for AS at the time of inclusion were eligible for participation, regardless of the type of therapy administered. No restrictions were applied concerning the therapeutic regimen.

Sample size

To determine the sample size, data provided by the NHIF registers were taken into account. According to the documentation, the number of registered patients in the Ruse region diagnosed with AS (ICD code M45) for 2024 is 207. The study aims to cover one-third of patients with AS in the region in order for the data to be considered reliable, which is approximately 60 patients.

Data collection instruments

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire containing closed- and open-ended questions, organized into three modules:

1. Demographic and socio-medical data – age, sex, education, comorbidities, type and duration of the applied therapy, time to diagnosis, and health-behavioral habits;
2. Assessment of disease activity – using the Bath Ankylosing Spondylitis Disease Activity Index (BASDAI).
3. Assessment of medication adherence – using the validated Morisky 8-Item Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-8).

Assessment of disease activity

BASDAI is a self-assessment tool, a validated questionnaire for assessing disease activity in patients with AS. It includes six questions and integrates information about the level of overall fatigue, morning stiffness, pain in the spine, peripheral joints, and tendon insertion sites (Garrett et al. 1994). Scores range from 0 to 10, with values ≥ 4 considered indicative of an active form of the disease. Table 1 presents the interpretation of the index values.

Table 1. BASDAI values.

BASDAI score	Interpretation
0–2	Minimal or no disease activity. Symptoms are mild or controlled.
2–4	Mild to moderate complaints. Disease activity is present but not severe.
≥ 4	High disease activity. This is the threshold value at which a change in therapy is usually considered (e.g., initiation of biological therapy).
8–10	Very high activity – severe symptoms, markedly impaired quality of life.

Assessment of adherence level

MMAS-8 is a self-assessment, validated questionnaire consisting of eight questions related to the patient's behavior regarding the intake of prescribed medicines. The questions assess forgetfulness, carelessness, discontinuation when feeling better or in the presence of side effects, and similar behaviors (Berlowitz et al. 2017). The total score ranges from 0 to 8, with a higher score indicating better adherence to the prescribed medication therapy.

Based on the total score, patients are categorized into three groups, and the interpretation of the values is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Interpretation of MMAS-8 values.

Total score (MMAS-8)	Adherence level
< 6	Low adherence
6.0–7.9	Moderate adherence
8	High adherence

Data collection was performed by pharmacists specifically trained for this purpose by conducting face-to-face interviews in the pharmacies. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection. Participants received detailed information regarding the study objectives, procedures, and intended use of the results and confirmed their voluntary participation, with the right to withdraw at any time without consequences. No personal identifying information was collected. During data entry, coding was used to ensure the anonymity of respondents and the confidentiality of the information. Access to the data was restricted exclusively to the principal investigator, and the dataset was stored on a password-protected personal computer.

Statistical analysis of the data was performed using specialized statistical software, IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, version 26. Quantitative variables are presented as mean and standard deviation (mean \pm SD). Categorical (qualitative) variables are described as absolute numbers and relative shares (N, %). Parametric and non-parametric tests were used to test hypotheses. Correlation and regression analyses were also conducted. To assess the relationship between the level of medication adherence and disease activity, correlation analyses (Pearson and Spearman) were used. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Characteristics of the study population

A total of 66 patients diagnosed with ankylosing spondylitis were included in the study. Of them, 38 (57.6%) were men and 28 (42.4%) were women. More than three-quarters of all participants (74.3%) at the time of the interview were aged between 31 and 50 years, and the highest percentage were patients diagnosed with AS in the third decade of their life. The overall characteristics of the study population are presented in Table 3.

Medication adherence level

The level of adherence to prescribed medication therapy was assessed using the validated Morisky 8-Item Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-8). Low adherence (MMAS-8 < 6) was found in 36 patients (54.5%), moderate adherence (6.0–7.9) in 22 patients (33.3%), and high adherence (MMAS-8 = 8) in eight patients (12.1%). The results presented in Table 4 show a predominantly low to

Table 3. Demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population.

Characteristic	Category	Number	%
Sex	Male	38	58
	Female	28	42
Age, years	31–40 years	17	25.8
	41–50 years	32	48.5
	51–60 years	13	19.7
	Over 60 years	4	6.1
Time since AS diagnosis	Under 5 years	23	34.8
	5 to 10 years	31	47
	Over 10 years	12	18.2
Age at AS diagnosis	21–30 years	35	53
	31–40 years	13	19.7
	41–50 years	5	7.6
	51–60 years	3	4.5
	Over 60 years	1	1.5
Education level	Primary	2	3
	Secondary	21	32
	Higher	43	65
Comorbidities	Yes	47	71
	No	19	29
Biological therapy	Yes	43	65
	No	23	35
Non-pharmacological therapy	Yes	40	60
	No	26	40

Table 4. Distribution and descriptive statistics of medication adherence according to MMAS-8.

Indicator	n (%)	Value
MMAS-8 categories		
< 6 (low adherence)	36 (54.5%)	—
6.0–7.9 (moderate adherence)	22 (33.3%)	—
= 8 (high adherence)	8 (12.1%)	—
Descriptive statistics		
Minimum value	—	2.50
Maximum value	—	8.00
Mean value (mean ± SD)	—	5.696 ± 1.515
Median	—	5.500
Coefficient of variation (CV, %)	—	26.593

Table 6. Factors influencing medication adherence level.

Factor	Group	N	Mean Morisky score	SD	CV (%)	p-value
Sex	Men	38	5.62	1.26	22	0.640
	Women	28	5.80	1.82	31.40	
Education	Primary	2	7.69	0.12	1.60	<0.001
	Secondary	21	7.43	1.34	18	
	Higher	43	4.50	1.80	39.90	
Comorbidities	Without comorbidities	19	5.86	1.62	27.70	0.546
	With comorbidities	47	5.60	1.48	26.50	
Biological therapy	Without biological therapy	35	5.63	1.66	29.50	0.697
	With biological therapy	31	5.78	1.36	23.50	
Non-pharmacological intervention	Without non-pharmacological intervention	20	5.19	1.74	33.60	0.072
	With non-pharmacological intervention	46	5.92	1.37	23.10	

moderate level of adherence in the study group. The distribution of patients according to the level of adherence to therapy is presented in Table 4.

Disease activity

Assessment of disease activity using BASDAI showed that 46 patients (69.7%) had BASDAI values ≥ 4 , corresponding to an active form of the disease. BASDAI values ranged from 2.17–9.30, with the largest share of patients (43.9%) having values between five and seven, reflecting moderate to high disease activity. Extremely high activity (BASDAI > 8) was recorded in eight patients (12.1%). The distribution of patients by BASDAI categories is presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Distribution and descriptive statistics of disease activity according to BASDAI.

Indicator	n (%)	Value
BASDAI groups		
0–2 (very low activity)	0 (0.0%)	—
2–4 (low activity)	20 (30.3%)	—
≥ 4 (active disease)	46 (69.7%)	—
8–10 (very high activity)	8 (12.1%)	—
Descriptive statistics		
Minimum value	—	2.17
Maximum value	—	9.30
Mean value (Mean ± SD)	—	5.53 ± 2.15
Median	—	5.86
Coefficient of variation (CV, %)	—	38.9

Factors influencing medication adherence level

The influence of sex, education level, presence of comorbidities, and type of therapy – biological and non-pharmacological – on the level of adherence to prescribed therapy, measured by the Morisky MMAS-8 score, was investigated. The obtained results are presented in Table 6.

Factor analysis showed that educational level has a statistically significant effect on adherence. Patients with primary and secondary education demonstrate significantly higher mean Morisky scores compared with patients with higher

education ($p < 0.001$), in whom the lowest mean adherence and the greatest variability of results were observed.

No statistically significant difference in adherence was found between the two sexes ($p = 0.640$), as well as with regard to the presence of comorbidities ($p = 0.546$) and the use of biological therapy ($p = 0.697$). These results indicate that the listed factors do not independently exert a substantial influence on the overall level of adherence in the studied population.

The categorical analysis confirmed that educational level is most strongly associated with adherence, with patients with higher education more often having low adherence, while those with secondary education demon-

strate higher levels ($p < 0.001$). With regard to sex and the presence of comorbidities, borderline or moderately significant differences are observed, while the type of therapy does not have a substantial influence (Table 7).

Factors influencing disease activity

Factor analysis of disease activity shows that disease activity is statistically significantly higher in women, patients with comorbidities, smokers, and those who do not exercise, whereas the use of biological therapy is associated with lower BASDAI values ($p < 0.05$). The remaining studied factors do not show an independent significant influence (Table 8).

Table 7. Categorical distribution of medication adherence levels by influencing factors (number of patients).

Factor	Group	< 6 pts (low)	6–7.99 pts (moderate)	8 pts (high)	p-value
Sex	Men (n = 38)	25	10	3	p = 0.051
	Women (n = 28)	10	13	5	
Education	Primary (n = 2)	0	2	0	p < 0.001
	Secondary (n = 21)	3	10	8	
	Higher (n = 43)	32	11	0	
Non-pharmacological methods	Without non-pharmacological treatment	12	5	1	p = 0.605
	With non-pharmacological treatment	24	17	7	
Comorbidities	Without comorbidities	12	10	2	p ≈ 0.0176
	With comorbidities	24	15	3	
Biological therapy	Without biological therapy	19	9	3	p = 0.872
	With biological therapy	17	13	5	

Table 8. Analysis of factors influencing disease activity.

Factor	N	Mean BASDAI	SD	CV (%)	P value
Sex					
Men	38	5.02	2.17	43.2%	p = 0.031
Women	28	6.22	1.97	31.7%	
Comorbidities					
Without comorbidities	19	3.42	1.66	48.4%	p = 0.000001
With comorbidities	47	6.40	1.72	26.8%	
Diet					
Without diet	28	5.11	2.14	41.9%	p = 0.101
With diet	38	6.02	1.83	30.4%	
Biological therapy use					
Without biological therapy	23	6.73	1.30	19.3%	p = 0.000006
With biological therapy	43	4.57	1.51	33.1%	
Non-pharmacological methods					
Without non-pharmacological treatment	26	5.21	2.03	39.0%	p = 0.102
With non-pharmacological treatment	40	6.00	1.78	29.7%	
Physical activity					
Physically inactive	31	6.07	2.14	35.2	p = 0.019
Exercising	35	5.05	2.08	41.3	
Smoking					
Non-smokers	37	4.61	1.90	41.2	p ≈ 3.5 × 10 ⁻⁵
Smokers	29	6.70	1.90	28.3	
Sleep duration					
Sleep less than 6 h	46	5.90	1.64	27.8	p = 0.029
Sleep more than 6 h	20	4.68	2.91	62.1	
BMI					
Normal weight, BMI <25	31	5.18	2.05	39.6%	P = 0.39
Overweight, BMI ≥ 25	35	5.84	2.22	38.1%	

To examine the relationships between adherence level and disease activity, a correlation analysis was conducted between the main variables – sex, disease activity, and medication adherence level – for the entire study population, and the obtained results are presented in Table 9.

Table 9. Correlation analysis between medication adherence, disease activity, and sex.

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation coefficient	p-value
MMAS-8 score	BASDAI score	$r = 0.45$ (Pearson)	< 0.001
MMAS-8 score	BASDAI score	$\rho = 0.37$ (Spearman)	< 0.001
Sex	BASDAI score	$r = 0.28$ (Pearson)	0.025
Sex	BASDAI score	$\rho = 0.27$ (Spearman)	0.030
Sex	MMAS-8 score	$r = 0.06$ (Pearson; n.s.)	> 0.05
Sex	MMAS-8 score	$\rho = 0.06$ (Spearman; n.s.)	> 0.05

The analysis revealed a statistically significant moderate positive correlation between medication adherence level, assessed by MMAS-8, and disease activity, measured by BASDAI (Pearson $r = 0.45$; Spearman $\rho = 0.37$; $p < 0.001$). This result indicates that patients with higher disease activity demonstrate higher levels of adherence to the prescribed treatment. A weak but statistically significant positive correlation between sex and disease activity was also found (Spearman $\rho = 0.27$; $p = 0.030$), indicating higher BASDAI values in women. No statistically significant correlation was found between sex and medication adherence level ($p > 0.05$).

Discussion

This study among patients with AS from the Ruse region of Bulgaria confirms the established trend for the disease to be prevalent mainly among young people, with a predominance of males (Rusman et al. 2018). A number of studies emphasize the problem of late diagnosis of the disease and untimely referral to a rheumatology specialist (Chan et al. 2024). The obtained results support this statement, as in nearly half of the patients included in the sample, the time to diagnosis was in the range of 5–10 years. The therapy used by patients is predominantly biological, which corresponds to established therapeutic practice and to data from a study including 17 European registries (Deodhar et al. 2020).

Analysis of medication adherence shows that low to moderate adherence predominates in the studied population, which is consistent with results from other studies in chronic inflammatory rheumatologic diseases (Malaviya and Ostör 2012). The observed tendency toward poor adherence to prescribed therapy is particularly concerning given the chronic and progressive nature of the disease and places affected individuals at risk of impaired quality of life and disability (Tolu et al. 2020).

The results for disease activity show higher BASDAI values (mean value 5.53) compared with the published results from the multicenter European EuroSpA study, where the mean value before initiation of biological

therapy was 4.8 ± 2.0 (Müller-Ladner et al. 2023; Reddy et al. 2024). This highlights that most of the patients in the studied sample are above the target level of control, and in them initiation or optimization of biological or targeted therapy is likely justified, as well as implementation of intensive non-pharmacological interventions.

Analysis of factors influencing medication adherence shows that educational level is a statistically significant determinant, with patients with higher education demonstrating lower adherence. Similar observations have been described in other studies, suggesting that higher educational level is associated with greater autonomy, a critical attitude toward long-term therapy, and a tendency to modify treatment independently (Kardas et al. 2013).

Factor analysis of disease activity confirms the importance of comorbidities, smoking, and lack of physical activity as unfavorable factors associated with higher BASDAI values. These results are consistent with available literature data emphasizing the role of modifiable risk factors in disease control (Zhao et al. 2017; Exarchou et al. 2022). At the same time, the lower disease activity observed in patients on biological therapy corresponds to the proven effectiveness of biological disease-modifying medicines in ankylosing spondylitis (Webers et al. 2023).

One of the most significant results is the observed moderate positive correlation between adherence level and disease activity, measured by BASDAI. A similar association has been described in other studies, where it is assumed that patients with more pronounced symptoms are more motivated to follow the prescribed treatment (Navarro-Compán et al. 2021). This supports the concept of a reverse causal relationship in which subjective symptom perception influences therapeutic behavior, especially in chronic diseases with variable clinical activity (Glasser et al. 2022).

Correlation analysis showed that sex does not directly influence adherence but is significantly associated with higher BASDAI values in women. Therefore, the influence of sex on the “adherence–disease activity” relationship is indirect, mediated by the level of disease activity. In practice, this suggests the need for additional support and reminder mechanisms during periods of remission, when patients tend to miss doses due to lower disease activity.

The obtained results underline the need for systematic monitoring of adherence to therapy and early identification of patients at risk of non-adherence. A number of publications show that pharmaceutical interventions, including education, therapy monitoring, and an appropriate individualized approach and communication, can improve adherence and clinical outcomes in chronic arthritic diseases (Barat et al. 2024).

Limitations of the study

This study has several limitations that should be taken into account. The cross-sectional design does not allow tracking the dynamics of the studied indicators over time and does not allow establishing causal relationships between medication adherence and disease activity. The regional

nature of the study limits the possibility of generalizing the results to the entire Bulgarian population of patients with AS. The obtained data reflect the characteristics of a specific study group from the Ruse region of Bulgaria. An additional limitation is the lack of a sufficient number of national studies investigating medication adherence and disease activity in patients with AS, which hinders the comparability of the obtained results. The self-assessment instruments used – BASDAI and MMAS-8 – rely on subjective responses from patients and may be influenced by individual differences in symptom perception and therapeutic behavior, which carries a risk of bias in the obtained results.

Despite the reported limitations, this analysis contributes real-world data and supports the need for future longitudinal studies aimed at better understanding the dynamics over time and the relationship between adherence to therapy and disease activity in patients with AS.

Conclusion

This pilot study demonstrates that patients with AS in the studied Bulgarian population exhibit predominantly low to moderate medication adherence, while a substantial proportion present with moderate to high disease activity. These findings indicate suboptimal disease control in real-world practice and highlight adherence as a clinically relevant concern.

A key result is the statistically significant moderate positive correlation between medication adherence and disease activity. This suggests that adherence behavior in AS is dynamic and symptom-driven, with patients demonstrating higher adherence during periods of increased disease activity. This finding supports the concept of a reverse causal relationship in which perceived symptom burden influences therapeutic engagement, rather than adherence functioning solely as an independent determinant of disease control.

Educational level emerged as a significant predictor of adherence, with lower adherence observed among patients with higher education, indicating the need for individualized communication strategies and shared decision-making approaches tailored to patient profiles. Disease activity was significantly influenced by sex, comorbidities, smoking, physical inactivity, and the use of biological therapy, underscoring the importance of comprehensive management that integrates pharmacological and lifestyle-related factors.

From a clinical and pharmaceutical perspective, these results emphasize the necessity of systematic adherence monitoring, particularly during periods of lower disease activity when the risk of non-adherence may increase.

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The findings support the implementation of structured pharmaceutical care interventions and reinforce the role of pharmacists as active members of the multidisciplinary team in optimizing long-term disease control.

Although limited by its cross-sectional design and regional scope, this study provides real-world evidence that contributes to understanding the complex relationship between adherence behavior and clinical outcomes in AS. Larger longitudinal studies incorporating both subjective and objective adherence measures are warranted to further clarify causal pathways and inform targeted interventions.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The research study among patients with ankylosing spondylitis in the Ruse region was approved by the Commission on Ethics of Scientific Research (CESR) at the Medical University of Varna, Protocol 5 of 17 October 2024.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

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Author contributions

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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